

susceptible; 5, resistant; and 3, moderately resistant. Results indicated that the Pattambi BPH population is likely to be less virulent than that at Raipur or Hyderabad. □

Evaluating rice cultivars for yellow stem borer (YSB) resistance

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Forty-one rice cultivars were screened for field resistance to YSB during 1988 at the Rice Research Station, Tirur, India.

Seedlings (30-d-old) for each entry were spaced at 20 × 10 cm in three 4-m rows in a randomized block design with three replications. Susceptible check Jaya was planted in single rows between entries in each replication and in three rows between replications.

Deadheart was counted 15, 30, and 45 d after transplanting (DT) and whitehead at 10 d before harvest for 20 randomly selected hills for each entry. Infestation was scored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES).

W1263 was resistant at 15 DT and moderately resistant at other times. TM8089, TM2011, and CO 43 were moderately susceptible at 15 and 30 DT. TKM9 was moderately susceptible at all times (see table). □

Field reaction^a of rice varieties to YSB under natural infestation, Tirur, India, 1988.

Accession	Parentage	Deadheart score ^b			Whitehead score 10 d before harvest
		15 DT	30 DT	45 DT	
TM8089	Selffrom TKM9	5	5	7	9
TM2011	C22/TKM6/TR50	5	5	7	9
TM4640	BAM3/IR50	5	7	7	9
TM4309	BAM3/IR50	5	7	7	7
TPS1	IR8/Kattaisamba	7	7	7	9
PMK1	CO 25/ADT31	7	7	7	9
IET7511	Ras/Barket	7	7	7	9
TKM9	TKM7/IR8	5	5	5	5
ADT37	BG280-2/PTB33	7	7	7	9
TM6012	C22/BJ1	7	7	7	3
TM5656	IR50/TKM9	7	7	7	9
TM5118	BAM3/IR50	7	7	7	9
TM10232	TKM6/IET1444	7	7	7	9
TM1086	Ponni/ME80	5	7	7	7
TM5670	IR50/TKM9	7	7	7	9
TM4937	BAM3/IR50	7	7	7	9
TM4955	BAM3/IR50	7	7	7	9
TM4865	AC76/TKM8	7	7	7	9
TM8601	TKM9/ADT9/CR141/IR26	7	7	7	9
TM8381	IR262/CR1106-190	7	7	7	7
TM8602	CO 31/22	7	7	7	9
TM4300	IR262/Bhavani	7	7	7	9
TMA1087	Ponni/CH1039	7	7	7	7
TNAU891434	IET6262/TBAY1756	5	7	7	9
TNAU840337	TKM9/White Ponni	5	7	7	9
TNAU6790/2	BAM3/TN1	7	7	7	9
TNAU6540/2	GMR2/BAM3	7	7	7	7
TNAU843062	IET4141/CO43	5	7	7	9
PM1381	IR13564-149-3/ASD4	7	7	7	7
PM1340	IR13564/ASD4	7	7	7	7
MW10	MTU15/Yaikyakunantoku	7	7	7	9
AS26556	IET5233/IR2153-26-3-5-2	5	7	7	9
ACM38	ASD4/TKM6	9	7	9	9
CO 11	GEB24/ <i>O. perennis</i>	7	7	7	7
IR20	IR262/CR106-190	7	7	7	5
ADT38	IR1529/IR4432/IR7963	5	7	7	9
CO 43	Daral/IR20	5	5	7	9
ADT39	IR8/IR20	7	7	7	9
White Ponni	Tg 65/ME80	7	7	7	7
W1263	MTU15/Eswarakora	1	3	3	3
Jaya	TN1/T14	9	9	9	9

^aDeadheart and whitehead scores by SES. ^bDT = days after transplanting.

Field reaction of rice breeding lines to brown planthopper (BPH) in Pondicherry, India

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BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) is an important pest in Pondicherry region, especially in sornavari season (May to Aug/Sep). During 1988 and 1989 wet seasons (Jun-Sep) 143 entries of advanced rice breeding lines (including local susceptible and resistant checks) From the Directorate of Rice Research, Hyderabad, were screened in the field against BPH.

Field reaction of selected breeding lines to BPH in Pondicherry, India, 1988 and 1989 wet seasons.

Designation	Cross	BPH damage score ^a			Reaction to other pests ^b
		1988	1989	Mean	
BPT2217	BPT3291/ARC6650	3	1	2	—
BPT4363	BPT3291/Velluthacheera	3	1	2	—
BPT4365	BPT3291/Velluthacheera	3	1	2	—
RP1579-13-11-12	Phalguni/ARC6650	5	3	4	RTV-P
RP1746-1723-8	RPA5824/RP79-9//Rasi//PTB21	3	3	3	LF-S
RP2332-16-3	Ratna/ARC10654	3	3	3	LF-S
RP2332-18-15	Ratna/ARC10654	3	3	3	LF-S
RP2332-19-9-6	Ratna/ARC10654	3	3	3	—
RP2362-227-22	Nagarjuna/ARC5989	3	3	3	—
RP2542-1657-194	Swarnadhan/RP1579-37	3	3	3	—
RP2.543-1444-46	Rasi/RP1579-38	3	3	3	—
RP2.543-1464-152	Rasi/RP1579-38	3	3	3	—
RP2547-985-100	RP2205/RP1579-38	5	5	5	—
RP2547-1059-118	RP2205/RP1579-38	5	5	5	—
IR50 (local susceptible check)	—	9	9	9	—
ADT36 (local check)	—	3	3	3	—
PY3 (local resistant check)	—	1	3	2	LF-S
TN1 (standard susceptible check)	—	9	9	9	—

^aBy the *Standard evaluation system for rice*. ^bRTV-P = rice tungro virus present, LF-S = leafhopper susceptible.

Test entries were planted in two rows of 10 hills each, alternated with a skip row of susceptible check TN1. Closer spacing (15 × 10 cm) and a topdressing of extra N above the recommended dose were used to induce higher BPH incidence in the trials. We scored entries in the field during peak BPH incidence and when TN1 died.

Promising entries that recorded BPH damage score of 2-3 were BPT2217, BPT4363, BPT4365, RP2332-19-9-6, RP2362-227-22, RP2542-1657-194, RP2543-1444-46, RP2543-1464-152, local check ADT36, and local resistant check PY3 (see table). RP1746-1723-8, RP2332-16-3, and RP2332-18-15 were resistant to BPH (score 3), but susceptible to leafhopper. □

Sources of resistance to brown planthopper (BPH) in rice

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We studied 108 rice cultivars to identify sources of resistance to the local biotype of BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) under laboratory conditions using the bulk seedling test.

Test entries were sown in 20-cm rows, 5 cm apart, in 60- × 45- × 10-cm wooden boxes at Rice Research Station, Moncompu, Kerala, from 1985 to 1988. Each box contained 24 lines including four of susceptible check TN1 and two of resistant check PTB33.

Seedlings were thinned to 20 per row at 7 d. Seedboxes were placed inside 70- × 55- × 15-cm trays with 5 cm of water in them. Trays were kept inside a screening cage. After 1 wk each seedling was infested with an average of five second-instar BPH nymphs. Damage was scored by the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES) scale when about 90% of TN1 had died. Screening was repeated three times.

Forty rice cultivars were resistant (see table), 22 moderately resistant, 13 moderately susceptible, and 33 highly susceptible. Resistant entries were of diverse origin: Indonesia (1), Sri Lanka (3), Philippines (7), and India (29). Of the Indian types, 13 (and PTB33) were from Kerala. □

Resistant entries and BPH score.^a

Designation	Origin	Damage score (0-9)	Designation	Origin	Damage score (0-9)
Sinna Sivappu	Sri Lanka	2.9	RP1015-45-114-1	India	1.8
Lekham Samba	Sri Lanka	2.6	KAU1734-2 ^b	India	2.9
Kuru Hondarawala	Sri Lanka	1.2	RP1015-100-25-4	India	2.7
IR40	Philippines	2.4	KAU2084 ^b	India	1.2
IR25984-92-1-3	Philippines	2.5	KAU169 ^b	India	2.7
IR1552	Philippines	1.2	KAU126 ^b	India	2.6
IR5741-73-2-3	Philippines	2.8	KAU153-1 ^b	India	1.6
IR22082-41-2	Philippines	2.1	KAU168 ^b	India	2.7
IR24	Philippines	2.5	KAU93 ^b	India	2.2
IR9830-26-3-3	Philippines	2.7	MO 4 ^b	India	2.8
CR266-407-4	India	1.2	MO 5 ^b	India	2.6
RP2695-5-7-32	India	1.5	MO 6 ^b	India	2.0
RP2068-32-2-2	India	1.6	MO 7 ^b	India	2.0
MTU5194	India	1.7	M102 ^b	India	2.9
RP2695-5-8-31	India	1.9	RP1015-15-7-7-2	India	2.9
MTU5295	India	1.7	RP1579-73-1864	India	2.8
RP2068-17-2-2	India	1.6	RP1579-1863-73-32-53	India	2.8
RP1579-56-1907	India	1.6	ARC6650	India	2.9
RP1756-39	India	1.4	M66-B-45-1	Indonesia	1.8
TNAU BPHR8275	India	2.4	PTB33 (resistant check) ^b	India	2.4
MTU4870	India	1.6	TN1 (susceptible check)	Taiwan	8.7

^aScored by SES. All entries except TN1 were resistant. ^bFrom Kerala.

Virulence of a new biotype of brown planthopper (BPH) in Mekong Delta

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Six BPH populations from five ecological areas in the Mekong Delta were collected to determine their virulence on rice using the modified bulk seedling test.

Differential check varieties were seeded in 20-cm rows, 5 cm apart, in 60- × 40- × 10-cm seedboxes with three replications. Test varieties were infested 7 d after seeding with 5-8 second- and third-instar nymphs per seedling. Damage was visually rated using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (1-9) when the susceptible check TN1 had died.

All new biotype populations killed TN1. Mudgo (*Bph 1*) was moderately

Reaction^a of BPH on differential check varieties, Mekong Delta, 1990-91.

Site, season	Host of BPH population	BPH score ^a on					
		TN1 (none)	Mudgo (<i>Bph 1</i>)	ASD7 (<i>bph 2</i>)	Rathu Heenati (<i>Bph 3</i>)	PTB33 (digenic)	Babawee (<i>bph 4</i>)
Angiang	IR64	9	7	9	3	3	3
1990 WS		9	7	7	3	0	3
1991 DS	MTL 85	9	7	7	0	1	5
Angiang		9	5	9	5	0	3
1990 WS	MTL 85	9	5	7	5	0	5
1991 DS		9	5	9	5	0	5
Tiengiang	OM59-7	9	5	7	3	1	1
1990 WS		9	5	9	3	1	5
1991 DS	IR42	9	3	7	1	0	7
Haugiang		9	3	7	1	0	7
1990 WS	IR19660	9	7	9	5	0	5
1991 DS		9	7	9	5	0	5

^aAv of 3 replications. By the *Standard evaluation system for rice* scale.